

THE FORMULATION OF A CURVED COMPOSITE BRICK FINITE ELEMENT USING A LAYER-WISE THEORY

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ABSTRACT

The finite element method (FEM) is a powerful analysis tool for the design of structures and is widely used in many fields including the analysis of composite structures. Problems arise, however, when considering large structures, such as are found in the marine fields, due to the huge disparity between the scale of the structure and the scale of the composite materials used to produce it. Such structures can be adequately modelled if their construction is simple and the loading is primarily in-plane, but if the geometry of the structure is complex or the loading regime creates significant through-thickness effects then the level of detail required to adequately model the material results in excessively large models to represent the structure. Modern computing facilities can comfortably process such models, but the man-hours required to develop them makes them prohibitively expensive. The work described in this paper has aimed to overcome this problem by the development of a finite element capable of accurately modelling a complex composite structure even when it is coarsely defined over the structure. This greatly simplifies the modelling process thereby economically allowing FEM to be applied to such structures at an early stage in their design.

INTRODUCTION

An experimental and theoretical programme has been on-going in the Department of Ship Science for several years investigating the behaviour of out-of-plane joints in large ship-type composite structures [1]. These joints typically comprise of a curved overlaminates joining the out-of-plane structural members, laminated over a flexible fillet. Modelling the isotropic fillet and the flat composite panels can be done with relative crudity without greatly affecting the accuracy of the results, but the combination of curvature and composite material properties in the overlaminates requires that the FE model be sufficiently defined to overcome the limitations and assumptions of the particular element formulation being used. The most limiting assumptions that affect this problem are that:

- a: the element is assumed to be flat, and
- b: properties are constant through the thickness.

The assumption of flatness has several implications when trying to model a curved surface. Firstly the elements form a series of flats between nodes as opposed to a smooth curve, with each element having the sides at the layer ends angled instead of square. This results in incorrect geometric properties being derived through the thickness of the element, thus model

definition must be increased in this direction. Secondly, there is no coupling between the in-plane and through-thickness directions within the element in the direction of curvature, thus model definition must be increased in this direction also.

The assumption of constant properties through the thickness results from the composite elements being derived from isotropic element formulations, with the composite layer properties being averaged across the element to give a nominal element property. This gives reasonable results in the in-plane directions for flat elements, but if the element is curved or through thickness behaviour is important then element definition must be increased in the through-thickness direction.

The resulting high level of definition required to model the curved overlaminates imposes a similar level of definition in the surrounding regions, and ultimately has an influence on the whole model. This is not such a problem when modelling small structural details, but when a large structure such as a ship is being modelled this level of definition, though desirable, is not practical in terms of the man-hours required to produce the model.

Several more advanced formulations have been developed that are able to model curvature, for example the "sublaminates analysis method" described by Flanagan [2], and others are able to model each layer in the through-thickness direction, such as the "generalised layer-wise plate theory" of Reddy [3], but for the case of the curved overlaminates both of these areas need to be modelled together. In this paper an element formulation has been proposed that models both curvature and through-thickness variations in such a manner as to obviate the need for such highly defined models as are currently required.

FORMULATION OF NUMERICAL MODEL

ASSUMPTIONS AND RESTRICTIONS

Since the ultimate aim of this analytical model is that it can be used to analyse large and complex structures assumptions and restrictions have been kept to a minimum, and the formulation has been kept as general as possible. Nevertheless of necessity some restrictions have been applied.

a: Curvature is cylindrical. This assumption is made primarily because when the majority of composite reinforcing materials are draped over three dimensionally curved surfaces the orientation of the fibres are changed relative to each other (the materials that don't do this do not drape at all). This change needs to be modelled and this cannot readily be done within a single

Figure 1. Arrangement of numerical model

element without a very complex material property formulation. Thus increased element definition is required to model this phenomenon, and this increased definition means that a series of two dimensionally curved elements can adequately model a three dimensionally curved surface. This greatly simplifies the element formulation since coupling terms are only required in one direction, around the curvature.

b: Material properties are constant within each layer. This means that in a given direction the material properties are the same across the width and through the thickness of the layer. No attempt is made to model the fibre and matrix, or the interface between them. This is a "standard" ("phenomenological") assumption made by most formulations to reduce the necessary level of modelling detail. It is not strictly accurate but if averaged layer properties and failure values are used it is representative.

c: Deflections are small. This assumption is made not so much to simplify the displacement function, though this does result, but also to simplify the relationships between vectors acting at element nodes and their equivalent acting at layer nodes.

DETAILED RELATIONSHIPS

Basic geometric relationships

The general arrangement of the element is shown in Fig. 1. The element coordinate system (r,s,t) is located in the centre of the r,s plane at the outer face of the outer layer (ie. on the mould surface of a female mould). This allows general formulae for layer levers to be used without having to account for when they are above or below the origin of the coordinate system. Each layer coordinate system (ri,si,ti) is located at the centre of that layer. The r axes of all coordinate systems follow the curvature of the element.

Each element is defined by the eight nodes (N1–N8 in Fig. 1), the radius of curvature (R), and the angle of curvature (α). In addition the number of layers, their orientation and material makeup are also input. A database within the program stores material properties and layer thicknesses for a variety of common materials, and these are retrieved for each layer. Layer nodes (Ln,i in Fig. 1) are then assigned on each corner of each layer, at the top and bottom surfaces, and layer geometric properties (areas and lengths) are calculated. When, for example, a calculation is made on the interface between two layers, these geometric properties are recalculated to ensure realistic values are used at each location within the element.

The numerical formulation uses an approach similar to the layer-wise theory of Reddy [3], in that each layer is modelled separately with continuity maintained between layers with suitable relationships. It differs slightly in that the layers are modelled as three dimensional bodies, with the link between layers being the continuity between adjacent layer nodes. This ensures that these relationships are independent of the location in the element and thus not involved in any differentiation or integration. Displacement continuity between layers is maintained by the use of a linear displacement function.

Layer displacement function.

The displacement function is based on the "non-conforming" element of Taylor et al [4]. The higher order extra terms are not included at this stage for simplicity, and coupling terms are included to model the curvature. The function is three dimensional and it has the form:

$$[u_{(r,s,t)}] = [A] [u_{ln}] \quad (1)$$

The coupling terms in the displacement function [A] are derived according to the following (terms are illustrated in Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Nomenclature for derivation of curvature terms.

For a point with ordinate r around a curved laminate, the angle through which a vector at position -1 must be compounded to determine its influence at r is given by θ , which is $\alpha/2$ multiplied by the distance from -1 to r . This is given by

$$-(\alpha/2(-1-r)) \tag{2}$$

A vector at position $+1$ must be compounded through an angle of $\alpha-\theta$ which is given by

$$(\alpha/2(1-r)) \tag{3}$$

Care must be taken to ensure the correct sign is used, since this is a function of the vector location and direction. Positive vectors at -1 have a positive effect at r in the r direction (around the curve), but this is not so for other directions, or locations.

Stress/strain relationship

The relationship between stress and strain follows the generalized Hooke's law which, in matrix form is given by:

$$[\epsilon] = [D][\sigma] \tag{4}$$

Composite materials can have significantly different Poisson's ratios in different directions, for example ν_{rs} is not necessarily equal to ν_{rt} . However these properties are frequently not available and thus the ratios from the principle directions have been used or calculated from other material properties.

Element node to layer node relationships

Equations 1 and 4 exist for each layer in the laminate. The resulting matrices are multiplied together in the form

$$[K_L] = [B^T][D][B] \tag{5}$$

where $[B]$ is the differential of $[A]$ with respect to r , s and t as appropriate, and the superscript T indicate the transpose matrix. All of the resulting $[K_L]$, the layer stiffness matrices, are summed together to form the centre of the element stiffness matrix;

$$[K] = [K_{left}][K_{centre}][K_{right}] \tag{6}$$

$[K_{left}]$ and $[K_{right}]$ are the matrices governing the relationship between vectors of force and

displacement, respectively, at layer nodes (lnodes) and element nodes (enodes).

The force relationships are based on equilibrium, that is the force vectors acting in a given direction on two enodes in a particular corner (r,s location) are equivalent to the sum of the force vectors acting at the lnodes in the same corner in the same direction. For example, in the corner with (r,s) location (-1,-1);

$$F_{e1r} + F_{e5r} = \sum_{i=0}^{nl} F_{iir} \quad (7)$$

where F_{e1r} is the force at enode 1 acting in the r direction, and F_{iir} is the force acting at lnode i in layer i in the r direction. nl is the number of layers in the element.

Taking moments about enodes 1 and 5 respectively gives;

$$F_{e5r} \times \sum_{i=0}^{nl} t_i = \sum_{i=0}^{nl} (F_{iir} \times (\sum_{j=0}^i t_j)) \quad (8a)$$

and;

$$F_{e1r} \times \sum_{i=0}^{nl} t_i = \sum_{i=0}^{nl} (F_{iir} \times (\sum_{j=nl}^0 t_j)) \quad (8b)$$

where t_i is the thickness of layer i.

Equations 7 and 8 apply in the in-plane directions r and s. In the through-thickness direction, t, equilibrium combined with small deflection assumptions means that force is constant through the thickness, giving;

$$F_{lit} = F_{e1t} = F_{e5t} \quad (9)$$

The displacement relationships are based on assumptions of continuity, meaning that there must be no sudden changes in displacement between adjacent locations, and thus considering the same corner as for forces;

$$U_{iir} = U_{e1r} + ((U_{e5r} - U_{e1r}) \times ((\sum_{j=0}^i t_j) / \sum_{k=0}^{nl} t_k)) \quad (10)$$

Equation 10 is also valid in the s direction, but in the through-thickness, t, direction;

$$U_{lit} = U_{e1t} + ((U_{e5t} - U_{e1t}) \times ((\sum_{j=0}^i t_j / A_j E_j) / \sum_{k=0}^{nl} t_k / A_k E_k)) \quad (11)$$

Once [Kleft] and [Kright] are defined from equations 7-11 the stiffness matrix [K] is determined and integrated numerically over the element volume using $2 \times 2 \times nl$ integration points. Once a converged solution is achieved internal stresses and strains are determined by "sampling" a predetermined number of points. The number of points chosen affects the accuracy with which the distribution can be illustrated, not the accuracy of the values at the chosen points.

VALIDATION OF NUMERICAL MODEL

Table 1 shows the cross-sectional areas (CSA) calculated in the through-thickness direction, for a curved sandwich panel (illustrated in Fig. 3) made up of a 25mm foam core and two layers in each skin comprising an inner layer of CSM and an outer layer of WR, both in a polyester matrix (the sandwich panel was chosen as it more clearly illustrates the differences between the methods). The results are shown calculated by a coarse ANSYS FE model using one element through the thickness, a fine ANSYS FE model with five elements through the thickness, and the numerical model using one element. The ANSYS models all use the solid composite element stif46.

Table 1. Comparison of CSA used for element calculations

Location	Coarse F.E C.S.A.	Fine F.E C.S.A.	Numerical C.S.A.
A	2137.5	1787.5	1806.6
B	2137.5	1812.5	1831.9
C	2137.5	2137.5	2160.4
D	2137.5	2462.5	2488.9
E	2137.5	2487.5	2514.2

Figure 3. Illustration of foam panel showing location of values.

The numerical model calculates the areas at the integration points of each layer, which is used during the numerical integration, and then calculates the area at each point of interest during the calculation of stresses and strains. Mid-plane values are not used throughout each layer. The fine meshed (one element per layer) ANSYS FE model calculates the area of the mid-plane of each layer, but assumes each layer to be flat. These mid-plane values are used throughout each layer for all calculations. The coarse (one element through the laminate, the same as the numerical model) ANSYS FE model calculates the mid-plane area of the centre of the laminate, assuming it to be flat, and this is used for all calculations.

Table 2 compares results for a flat sandwich panel of a similar make-up to that in figure 7.3, with an in-plane displacement applied to it. Poisson's effects are ignored. Results have been calculated as before, with coarse and fine ANSYS FE models, and by a numerical model with one element. All three methods calculate the correct strain values, but the ANSYS FE requires a fine mesh to calculate the correct stress values in each layer. If the mesh is coarse the correct nodal values are calculated but then these are interpolated linearly through the thickness, resulting in a constant value. Clearly, if the material properties vary between layers, results from this type of model cannot be used to predict failure, although global force and deflection results will be reasonable. This level of accuracy is not significantly improved until the mesh is refined

Table 2. Comparison of stress values

Layer	Coarse F.E Stress MPa	Fine F.E Stress MPa	Numerical Stress MPa
A	587.2	587.2	587.2
B	587.2	266.7	266.7
C	587.2	9.2	9.2
D	587.2	266.7	266.7
E	587.2	587.2	587.2

such that all layers within an element have similar properties.

Further validation of the analytical model has been done by comparing stress results for an overlaminates from a typical out-of-plane joint [1] calculated using the ANSYS FEM program and the new formulation. The boundary angle is made up of 12 layers, 5 of woven roving (WR), and 7 of chopped strand mat (CSM), all in polyester resin, arranged as CSM CSM WR CSM CSM WR CSM CSM WR WR, from the outer to the inner layer. A combined bending and tension load is applied. Fig. 4a shows a contour plot of the in-plane stress in the overlaminates calculated using 22 elements within ANSYS, whilst Fig. 4b shows the in-plane stress calculated using one element of the new formulation.

Figure 4a. Contour plot of in-plane stress in overlaminates from ANSYS

Figure 4b. Graph of in-plane stress around overlaminates from new model

Fig. 4a shows a maximum stress value of 101MPa occurring towards the middle of the overlaminates, on the inner layer. The stress drops away towards the outer layer, and towards the ends. The graph in Fig. 4b shows a similar trend, with the maximum stress also occurring in the centre of the inner layer, and reducing towards the ends and the outer layer, but now the impact of each individual layer material property can be seen, with a clear distinction between the WR layers (in-plane modulus of 14GPa) at the top of the graph, and the CSM layers (in-plane modulus of 6.7GPa) at the bottom. The maximum stress value is slightly less at 97MPa in the innermost WR layer. The results shown in Fig. 4a are from an overlaminates that is part of a joint, and is attached to a flexible fillet around the outer layer. This tends to inhibit out-of-plane deflections, hence increasing in-plane stresses and reducing through-thickness stresses. This is illustrated in Figs. 5a and 5b, which show the through-thickness stresses in the FE model and the new formulation respectively.

Figure 5a. Contour plot of through-thickness stress in overlamine from ANSYS

Figure 5b. Graph of through-thickness stress around overlamine from new model

CONCLUSION

The numerical model, although in an early stage of development, has shown the potential of such a formulation to both simplify the definition of a large structure by reducing the number of elements required to define it, and to improve the detailed results in areas of curvature by the use of more appropriate geometric relationships.

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